

Underweight and Overweight among Rural School Children in Puducherry

Dharman Krishna Kumar

Institute of Allied Health Science
Srinivas University

Abstract

Malnutrition remains a significant public health challenge in India, particularly among children in rural areas. Malnutrition, encompassing both undernutrition and micronutrient deficiencies. Rural regions, due to socio-economic constraints, limited access to nutritious food, and inadequate health services, are disproportionately affected by malnutrition.

Objective: To determine the BMI based on the category of student, underweight and overweight among rural school children in Puducherry.

Study Design: This study was cross-sectional design to evaluate the nutritional status of rural school children in Puducherry. The study will include school children aged 6-12 years. A sample size of 286 children will be selected using stratified random sampling.

Results: Among the study population 286 average age of participants is 14 years, The 215 (75%) of them male were the 71 (25%) of them female participated. **Underweight Category (BMI <18) Study population 80** Approximately 27% of the population is underweight, indicating that more than a quarter of the individuals have a BMI less than 18. **Normal Weight Category (BMI 18-25) Around 73** About 25.5% of the population falls within the normal weight range. **Overweight and Obesity Category (BMI >25) 136** Nearly half (47.5%) of the population is either overweight.

Conclusion: Overweight and Obese Individuals: Interventions **Implement community-based programs focusing on healthy eating, physical activity, and weight management.** Underweight Individuals: Nutritional Support **Provide nutritional education. The data indicates significant health challenges within the population, with almost half being overweight or obese, and a notable portion being underweight.**

Keywords: Overweight, Underweight, BMI, Rural, Malnutrition, undernutrition, Weight

Introduction:

The childhood obesity estimated 8.4% also prevalence of childhood obesity 12.4%. male children found at risk of developing obesity compare to the female children. The percentage of overweight in the age of 6 to 12 age people were 4.41% also obesity in the Puducherry 2.12%. Most of the basic level nutrition about eating the regular, balance diet. The food you consume that will convert the nutrition to the body, brain muscle, circulation, bone, immune system. When a person does not get enough nutrients food in daily bases it continues longer time the person was developing malnutrition the weight loss, losses of appetite, fatigue may be a symptom.

There is a less conception of the essential nutrients, also calories deficiency meat the undernutrition. When the individual struggle to get prepare food same time improper diet patent, it will affect the growth of the individual. Regular diet patent the people not getting the vitamins and minerals which we called micronutrient, it is in less amount people may developed the deficiency also end with life threatening conditions.

The Body Mass Index (BMI) value derived from height and weight of person, measurement units for BMI Kg/ m². based on the BMI we categoric of underweight, overweight also Obesity is a chronic disease complex have excessive fat deposits in the body tissues. Obesity will lead to increased risk of diabetes and heart disease.

Malnutrition remains a significant public health challenge in India, particularly among children in rural areas. Malnutrition, encompassing both undernutrition and micronutrient deficiencies, adversely affects children's physical and cognitive development, school performance, and overall health. Rural regions, due to socio-economic constraints, limited access to nutritious food, and inadequate health services, are disproportionately affected by malnutrition.

Puducherry, despite its relatively high Human Development Index (HDI) compared to other Indian states, has rural pockets where children face nutritional challenges. Addressing malnutrition in these areas is crucial for ensuring the well-being and development of the next generation. Understanding the prevalence and determinants of malnutrition among school-aged children in rural Puducherry is essential for designing effective intervention strategies.

This cross-sectional study aims to assess the prevalence of malnutrition deficiency among rural school children in Puducherry and identify associated factors. The findings will provide insights into the nutritional status of children in this region and inform policies and programs aimed at improving child nutrition and health outcomes.

Method:

Study Design: This study will employ a cross-sectional design to evaluate the nutritional status of rural school children in Puducherry.

Study Population: The study will include school children aged 6-12 years attending rural schools in Puducherry. A sample size of 286 children will be selected using stratified random sampling to ensure representativeness.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Children aged 6-12 years enrolled in selected rural schools those who come at day of screening.
- Student who has willing to participated in the study.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Student who absents in day of screening.
- Student who not have willing to participated in the study.

Sample Size Calculation: Based on the estimated prevalence of malnutrition in rural areas, a sample size of 286 is calculated to achieve a confidence level of 95% and a margin of error of 5%.
Data Collection: Data will be collected using a structured questionnaire and anthropometric measurements. The questionnaire will be pre-tested for validity and reliability. The analysis part we plan to do the descriptive and inferential statistics. rates of undernutrition and micronutrient deficiencies will be calculated. Correlation analysis will be performed to identify factors associated with malnutrition.

Ethical Considerations: Ethical approval will be obtained from the institutional review board. VMRF DU – AHS (IRC. No: SAHS/IRC2023/002). Informed consent will be obtained from participated parents/guardians.

Result:

Descriptive Statistics

Table: 1 Basic Study Parameters

Variables	Mean± deviation	Std.	Maximum	Minium
Age	14±1.5		18	11
Gender	Male 215 (75%), Female 71(25%)			
Height	151±2		178	122
Weight	64±12		33	90
Wrist Circumference	16±2		150	26
Mid Arm Circumference	74±20		32	6.5

Among the study population 286 The average age of participants is 14 years, with a relatively low variability (SD = 1.5). Participants' ages range from 11 to 18 years. The 215 (75%) of them male were the 71 (25%) of them female participated. The average wrist circumference is 16 cm, with a low to moderate variability (SD = 2) Wrist circumferences range from 26 cm to 150 cm. The average Mid Arm circumference is 74 cm, with a low to moderate variability (SD = 20) Wrist circumferences range from 6.5 cm to 32 cm.

Fig 1 Gender Distribution

Fig: 1 shows the 75% of the population were male remaining 25% of them participated female.

Table: 2 Body Mass Index Category

BMI	Count	Percentage
<18	80	27 %
18-25	73	25.5 %
>25	136	47.5 %

Underweight Category (BMI <18) Study population 80 Approximately 27% of the population is underweight, indicating that more than a quarter of the individuals have a BMI less than 18. This suggests potential issues related to malnutrition, eating disorders, or other health conditions that prevent weight gain.

Normal Weight Category (BMI 18-25) Around 73 About 25.5% of the population falls within the normal weight range. This indicates that a quarter of the individuals have a BMI within the recommended range, which is generally associated with lower health risks compared to the other categories.

Overweight and Obesity Category (BMI >25) The 136 Nearly half (47.5%) of the population is either overweight or obese. This is a significant proportion, indicating a potential public health concern. High BMI values are often associated with increased risks of various health conditions such as cardiovascular diseases, diabetes, and certain cancers.

Fig: 2 BMI Distribution

Fig:2 show that BMI under 18 were 80 participated underweight, range between 18 to 25 was 73 participated normal weight and height, people with 25 above were 136 over weight. Its fig distribution has show that nearly off of the participated were the overweight.

Fig: 3 correlations between the height and weight based on there age compound

This plot seems as it plots height against weight, showing a linear relationship between the variable. Positive Correlation: There is a clear positive correlation between height and weight among the children and adolescents in the dataset. As expected, taller individuals tend to weigh more.

Age and Height (r)0.522 (p-value) 0.000 (significant at the 0.01 level) There is a moderate positive correlation between age and height. As age increases, height tends to increase. This relationship is statistically significant.

Height and Weight(r) 0.59 Significance (p-value) 0.000 (significant at the 0.01 level) There is a moderate positive correlation between height and weight. As height increases, weight tends to increase. This relationship is statistically significant.

Discussion:

Overweight and Obese Individuals(Interventions) Implement community-based programs focusing on healthy eating, physical activity, and weight management. Healthcare: Increase access to healthcare services for weight management and associated health conditions.

Underweight Individuals (Nutritional Support) Provide nutritional education and support to help individuals achieve a healthy weight. Medical Assessment: Encourage medical evaluations to identify underlying causes of low BMI, such as metabolic or eating disorders.

Conclusion:

The data indicates significant health challenges within the population, with almost half being overweight or obese, and a notable portion being underweight. Effective public health strategies and individual interventions are essential to address these issues and promote overall health and well-being.

Acknowledge:

Those all helped and guided all the way of study to completed, also mainly the study participated, school head master sir, also my college Mets.

Reference:

- 1.Sharma N, Sanjeevi RR, Balasubramanian K, Chahal A, Sharma A, Sidiq M. A Systematic Review on Prevalence of Overweight and Obesity among School Children and Adolescents in Indian Population. *Indian J Endocrinol Metab.* 2024 Mar-Apr;28(2):104-116. doi: 10.4103/ijem.ijem_365_23. Epub 2024 Apr 29. PMID: 38911116; PMCID: PMC11189280.
2. Sung M, Kumar A, Mishra R, Kulkarni B, Kim R, Subramanian SV. Temporal change in prevalence of BMI categories in India: patterns across States and Union territories of India, 1999-2021. *BMC Public Health.* 2024 May 16;24(1):1322. doi: 10.1186/s12889-024-18784-4. PMID: 38755591; PMCID: PMC11097587.
3. Pavithra G, Kumar SG, Roy G. Effectiveness of a community-based intervention on nutrition education of mothers of malnourished children in a rural coastal area of South India. *Indian J Public Health.* 2019 Jan-Mar;63(1):4-9. doi: 10.4103/ijph.IJPH_383_17. PMID: 30880730.
4. Smith JD, Fu E, Kobayashi MA. Prevention and Management of Childhood Obesity and Its Psychological and Health Comorbidities. *Annu Rev Clin Psychol.* 2020 May 7;16:351-378. doi: 10.1146/annurev-clinpsy-100219-060201. Epub 2020 Feb 25. PMID: 32097572; PMCID: PMC7259820.
5. Di Cesare M, Sorić M, Bovet P, Miranda JJ, Bhutta Z, Stevens GA, Laxmaiah A, Kengne AP, Bentham J. The epidemiological burden of obesity in childhood: a worldwide epidemic requiring urgent action. *BMC Med.* 2019 Nov 25;17(1):212. doi: 10.1186/s12916-019-1449-8. PMID: 31760948; PMCID: PMC6876113.
6. NCD Risk Factor Collaboration (NCD-RisC). Worldwide trends in body-mass index, underweight, overweight, and obesity from 1975 to 2016: a pooled analysis of 2416 population-based measurement studies in 128·9 million children, adolescents, and adults. *Lancet.* 2017 Dec 16;390(10113):2627-2642. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(17)32129-3. Epub 2017 Oct 10. PMID: 29029897; PMCID: PMC5735219.
7. Mittal M, Jain V. Management of Obesity and Its Complications in Children and Adolescents. *Indian J Pediatr.* 2021 Dec;88(12):1222-1234. doi: 10.1007/s12098-021-03913-3. Epub 2021 Oct 5. PMID: 34609654; PMCID: PMC8491444.
8. NCD Risk Factor Collaboration (NCD-RisC). Worldwide trends in underweight and obesity from 1990 to 2022: a pooled analysis of 3663 population-representative studies with 222 million children, adolescents, and adults. *Lancet.* 2024 Mar 16;403(10431):1027-1050. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(23)02750-2. Epub 2024 Feb 29. PMID: 38432237; PMCID: PMC7615769.
9. Tham KW, Abdul Ghani R, Cua SC, Deerochanawong C, Fojas M, Hocking S, Lee J, Nam TQ, Pathan F, Saboo B, Soegondo S, Somasundaram N, Yong AML, AshkenasJ, Webster N, Oldfield B. Obesity in South and Southeast Asia-A new consensus on care and management. *Obes Rev.* 2023

- Feb;24(2):e13520. doi: 10.1111/obr.13520. Epub 2022 Dec 1. PMID: 36453081; PMCID: PMC10078503.
10. Natarajan H, Shanthi Rani CS, Krishna Kumar D, Anjana RM, Ranjit U, Venkatesan U, Uma Sankari G, Pradeepa R, Mohan V, Deepa M. Future risk of diabetes among Indians with metabolic and phenotypic obesity: Results from the 10-year follow-up of the Chennai Urban Rural Epidemiology Study (CURES-158). *Acta Diabetol.* 2021 Aug;58(8):1051-1058. doi: 10.1007/s00592-021-01698-7. Epub 2021 Mar 23. PMID: 33759049.
 11. Shahid N, Salman F, Makhdum M. Major factors responsible for child malnutrition: A review. *J Pak Med Assoc.* 2021 Feb;71(2(B)):729-733. doi: 10.47391/JPMA.1243. PMID: 33941968.
 12. Banerjee R, Chahande J, Banerjee S, Radke U. Evaluation of relationship between nutritional status and oral health related quality of life in complete denture wearers. *Indian J Dent Res.* 2018 Sep-Oct;29(5):562-567. doi: 10.4103/ijdr.IJDR_285_17. PMID: 30409933.
 13. Biswas S, Pramanik KR, Sonowal CJ. Marginalised social groups differentials in nutritional status (BMI) among reproductive-aged women in West Bengal. *BMC Public Health.* 2023 May 10;23(1):842. doi: 10.1186/s12889-023-15635-6. PMID: 37165345; PMCID: PMC10170687.
 14. Panuganti P, Mehreen TS, Anjana RM, Mohan V, Mayer-Davis E, Ranjani H. Influence of Socioeconomic Status on Knowledge of Obesity and Diabetes among Adolescents in Chennai, South India. *Children (Basel).* 2017 Jul 25;4(8):61. doi: 10.3390/children4080061. PMID: 28757589; PMCID: PMC5575583.
 15. Njelekela MA, Muhihi A, Mpembeni RN, Anaeli A, Chillo O, Kubhoja S, Lujani B, Ngarashi D, Maghembe M. Knowledge and attitudes towards obesity among primary school children in Dar es Salaam, Tanzania. *Niger Med J.* 2015 Mar-Apr;56(2):103-8. doi: 10.4103/0300-1652.150692. PMID: 25838624; PMCID: PMC4382598.
 16. Stankiewicz M, Pieszko M, Sliwińska A, Małgorzewicz S, Wierucki Ł, Zdrojewski T, Wyrzykowski B, Łysiak-Szydłowska W. Obesity and diet awareness among Polish children and adolescents in small towns and villages. *Cent Eur J Public Health.* 2014 Mar;22(1):12-6. doi: 10.21101/cejph.a3813. PMID: 24844099.
 17. <http://www.ijedr.org/papers/IJSDR2212013.pdf>
 18. Ahmeda AF, Al-Ahmadi TF, Alotaibi AF, Alshehri MA, Almousa AM, Alshehri OM, Alanazi AZ, Anweigi LM. The awareness of water intake and its correlation with BMI among students attending national and international secondary schools in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. *Libyan J Med.* 2021 Dec;16(1):1918903. doi: 10.1080/19932820.2021.1918903. PMID: 33899704; PMCID: PMC8079079.
 19. Verjans-Janssen SRB, van de Kolk I, Van Kann DHH, Kremers SPJ, Gerards SMPL. Effectiveness of school-based physical activity and nutrition interventions with direct parental involvement on children's BMI and energy balance-related behaviors - A systematic review. *PLoS One.* 2018 Sep 27;13(9):e0204560. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0204560. PMID: 30261057; PMCID: PMC6160096.
 20. Purnell JQ. Definitions, Classification, and Epidemiology of Obesity. 2023 May 4. In: Feingold KR, Anawalt B, Blackman MR, Boyce A, Chrousos G, Corpas E, de Herder WW, Dhatariya K, Dungan K, Hofland J, Kalra S, Kaltsas G, Kapoor N, Koch C, Kopp P, Korbonits M, Kovacs CS, Kuohung W, Laferrère B, Levy M, McGee EA, McLachlan R, New M, Purnell J, Sahay R, Shah AS, Singer F, Sperling MA, Stratakis CA, Trencle DL, Wilson DP, editors. *Endotext* [Internet]. South Dartmouth (MA): MDText.com, Inc.; 2000-. PMID: 25905390.
 21. Fruh SM. Obesity: Risk factors, complications, and strategies for sustainable long-term weight management. *J Am Assoc Nurse Pract.* 2017 Oct;29(S1):S3-S14. doi: 10.1002/2327-6924.12510. PMID: 29024553; PMCID: PMC6088226.
 22. Putra, I.G.N.E., Daly, M., Sutin, A. *et al.* Obesity, psychological well-being related measures, and risk of seven non-communicable diseases: evidence from longitudinal studies of UK and US older adults. *Int J Obes* (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41366-024-01551-1>